

Equation containing fractional derivative and periodic boundary conditions

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Article Info	Abstract
Oral Presentation Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14332822	This paper is about the identification of the fractional diffusion problem with periodic boundary conditions. The existence, uniqueness as well as continuous dependence on data for the problem is presented with certain regularity and consistency conditions. Generalized Fourier method is utilized in this study. The algorithm of the method and an example are also presented to show the effectiveness and accuracy of the proposed method.
Keywords <i>Fourier method,</i> <i>Time fractional diffusion,</i> <i>Periodic boundary conditions</i>	

1. Introduction

Mathematical models play a substantial role in various fields of science such as thermoelasticity, engineering, medical science, control theory, chemical diffusion, etc., [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6]. Therefore, numerous researchers study on the construction of mathematical models which requires determination of unknown functions. At this stage, the inverse problems are taken into account for their determination. Generally, overdetermined conditions are utilized in the identification of unknown functions.

The definition of inverse problem can be articulated as determination of unknown feature of an object under consideration by employing overdetermined data obtained by using probing signals. Hence, the shape and features of the unknown object is determined by means of remote sensing and nondestructive testing which form a fundamental basis of the inverse problem. In real life, inverse problems have a great many of applications such as the identification of submarines, shoals of fish immersed in water. Moreover, in the identification of flying objects like airplanes and missiles, etc., inverse problems are used. Briefly, it is concluded that remote sensing provide a great advantage to form the overdetermined data and inverse problem as well [7].

Since analytical identification in inverse problems is a big challenge, various numerical methods such as implicit finite-difference schemes, Crank–Nicolson implicit finite-

difference formula, the fourth-order implicit scheme have been developed for the approximate identification [4]. Moreover, the stability of these finite different schemes is provided. Furthermore, compare to explicit finite-difference schemes, the implicit difference schemes spend most of the CPU time.

In recent years, time fractional differential problems including nonlocal boundary conditions have been under consideration to establish approximate or analytical solutions by utilizing various developed methods such as implicit finite difference schemes, semigroup method [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [12] [13] [14] [15].

In real life, periodic boundary conditions have been encountered in numerous processes such as diffusion problem and heat transfer, etc., [16] [17] [18] [19].

In this research, Fourier method is employed for the identification of time dependent unknown function in one-dimensional fractional diffusion problem involving periodic boundary conditions, by means of nonlocal overdetermined condition. The existence, uniqueness, and continuous dependence of the solution on the data for the inverse problem is provided by imposing regularity and consistency conditions.

The following time fractional diffusion problem is taken into consideration to identify the unknown time dependent function $r(t)$ and establish the solution $u(x,t)$ of the problem on

$\Omega := \{(x,t): 0 < x < \pi, 0 < t < T\}$ for a fixed number $T > 0$.

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$$\left(D_t^\alpha(u(x,t)) \right) = u_{xx}(x,t) + f(x,t), x > 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, t > 0, \tag{1}$$

$$u(0,t) = u(\pi,t), \tag{2}$$

$$u_x(0,t) = u_x(\pi,t), \tag{3}$$

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x), \tag{4}$$

where the functions $\varphi(x)$ on $[0,\pi]$ and $f(x,t)$ on $\bar{\Omega}$ are fixed.

2. Material and methods

For the solution of this problem, the Fourier Method and Picard successive approximations method were used.

3. Preliminary Results

This section is devoted to basic definitions and concepts utilized in this study [21] [22].

Definition: Let $v(\zeta, \theta)$ be a real valued function. Its Riemann-Liouville time fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$ is denoted by $I_t^\alpha v(\zeta, \theta)$ and is defined as:

$$I_\theta^\alpha v(\zeta, \theta) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^\theta \frac{v(\zeta,s)}{(\theta-s)^{1-\alpha}} ds.$$

Definition: The Caputo time fractional derivative of $v(\zeta, \theta)$ is defined as:

$$D_\theta^\alpha v(\zeta, \theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_0^\theta \frac{\partial^n v(\zeta,s)}{(\theta-s)^{1+\alpha-n}} ds, & n-1 < \alpha < n \\ \frac{\partial^n}{\partial \theta^n} v(\zeta, \theta), & \alpha = n \end{cases}$$

Definition: The Mittag-Leffler function of two parameters $E_{\alpha,\beta}(\zeta)$ is defined as

$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(\zeta) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta^j}{\Gamma(\alpha j + \beta)}$$

where $Re(\alpha) > 0, \zeta, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$.

3. Existence and Uniqueness for the Solution of Inverse Problem

$$D_t^\alpha(u(x,t)) = u_{xx}(x,t), x > 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, t > 0,$$

By employing SVM, the solution of the problem in above equations can be written in the following form:

$$u(x,t;\alpha) = X(x)T(t;\alpha) \tag{5}$$

where $0 \leq x \leq \pi, 0 \leq t \leq T$. Plugging Eq. (5) into Eq. (2) and arranging it, we have

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t,\alpha))}{T(t,\alpha)} = \frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} = -\gamma^2 \tag{6}$$

By taking the last equality from Eq. (6) and utilizing the boundary conditions in Eq. (2)-(3), we have the following problem:

$$X''(x) + \gamma^2 X(x) = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$X(0) = X(\pi), X'(0) = X'(\pi) \tag{8}$$

The problem in Eq. (7-8) is the well known Sturm-Liouville problem. The solution to this problem is as in Eq. (9):

$$X_{cn}(x) = \cos 2nx, X_{sn}(x) = \sin 2nx \tag{9}$$

where $k=1,2,\dots$ satisfy the equation and

$$\gamma_n = (2n)^2, \gamma_1 < \gamma_2 < \dots, n = 1,2, \dots$$

The second equation in Eq. (6) for eigenvalue yields the fractional differential equation below:

$$D_t^\alpha(T(t,\alpha)) + \gamma^2 T(t,\alpha) = 0 \tag{10}$$

$$T_n(t,\alpha) = E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha)$$

The solution of the problem (1)-(5) will be constructed in the following form:

$$u(x,t) = \left[\frac{u_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_{cn}(t) \cos(2nx) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_{sn}(t) \sin(2nx) \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha).$$

Utilization of the Fourier method leads us to determine the Fourier coefficients as follows:

$$u_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi f(\xi, \tau) d\xi d\tau,$$

$$u_{cn}(t) =$$

$$\varphi_{cn}(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) f(\xi, \tau) \cos(2n\xi) d\xi d\tau,$$

$$u_{sn}(t) =$$

$$\varphi_{sn}(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) f(\xi, \tau) \sin(2n\xi) d\xi d\tau,$$

where

$$\varphi_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) dx,$$

$$\varphi_{cn} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos(2nx) dx,$$

$$\varphi_{sn} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin(2nx) dx,$$

the solution of the problem (1)-(4) is established in the following form:

$$u(x,t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) f(\xi, \tau) d\xi d\tau \right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_{cn}(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) f(\xi, \tau) \cos(2n\xi) d\xi d\tau \right) \cos(2nx) +$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi_{sn}(t)E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) f(\xi, \tau) \sin(2n\xi) d\xi d\tau \sin(2nx) \\ & u(x, t) = \\ & \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) f(\xi, \tau) d\xi d\tau \right) + \\ & \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\varphi_{cn}(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) f_{cn}(t) dt \right) \cos(2nx) + \varphi_{sn}(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) + \\ & \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\varphi_{sn}(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) f_{sn}(t) dt \right) \sin(2nx) \end{aligned}$$

(6)

where

$$f_0(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) dx,$$

$$f_{cn}(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \cos(2nx) dx,$$

$$f_{sn}(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \sin(2nx) dx.$$

Theorem 1. The problem (1)–(5) has a unique solution under the following conditions:

- (S1) $\varphi(x) \in C^2([0, \pi])$, $\varphi(0) = \varphi(\pi)$, $\varphi'(0) = \varphi'(\pi)$,
- (S2) $f(x, t) \in C^{2,0}(\bar{\Omega})$, $f(0, t) = f(\pi, t)$, $f'(0, t) = f'(\pi, t)$, and $\int_0^\pi xf(x, t) dx \neq 0$.

Proof. The consistency conditions are obtained as

$$\varphi(0) = \varphi(\pi), \quad f(0, t) = f(\pi, t)$$

which are necessary for the solution $u(x, t)$ to be in $C^{2,1}(\Omega) \cap C^{1,0}(\bar{\Omega})$. Moreover, series (6) and its partial derivative with respect to x are uniformly convergent in $\bar{\Omega}$ under the smoothness conditions:

$$\varphi(x) \in C^2([0, \pi]) \text{ and } f(x, t) \in C^{2,0}(\Omega)$$

which is the implication of absolute convergence of t -partial derivative series with the conditions $\varphi'(0) = \varphi'(\pi)$, $f'(0, t) = f'(\pi, t)$ in $\bar{\Omega}$.

4. Stability of the solution

Theorem 2. The solution of the problem(1)-(4) constantly depend on the functions f, φ under the assumptions (S1)-(S3)

Proof. Let $F = \{(\varphi, f): \varphi \in C^2([0, \pi])$, and absolutely continuous, $f(x, t) \in C^{2,0}(\Omega)\}$ and its closure

$$\bar{F} = \{(\bar{\varphi}, \bar{E}, \bar{f}): \bar{\varphi} \in$$

$$C^2([0, \pi])$$
, and absolutely continuous, $\bar{f}(x, t) \in C^{2,0}(\Omega)\}$

be two sets of the data such that

$$\|f\|_{C^1(\Omega)} \leq M_1, \quad \|\bar{f}\|_{C^1(\Omega)} \leq M_1$$

$$\|\varphi\|_{C^2[0,\pi]} \leq M_2, \quad \|\bar{\varphi}\|_{C^2[0,\pi]} \leq M_2,$$

where

$M_i > 0, i = 1, 2$ are constants.

Let us denote $\|\Phi\| = (\|\varphi\|_{C^2[0,\pi]} + \|f\|_{C^{2,0}(\bar{\Omega})})$. Let u and \bar{u} be solutions of the problems (1)-(5) corresponding to the data (φ, f) and $(\bar{\varphi}, \bar{f})$.

$$u(x, t) - \bar{u}(x, t)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & = \frac{1}{2} \left((\varphi_0 - \bar{\varphi}_0) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t (f_0(\tau) - \bar{f}_0(\tau)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2t^\alpha) d\tau \right) \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \cos(2kx) [(\varphi_{ck} - \bar{\varphi}_{ck}) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2t^\alpha) + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \sin(2kx) [(\varphi_{sk} - \bar{\varphi}_{sk}) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2t^\alpha) + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \cos(2kx) \int_0^t (f_{ck}(\tau) - \bar{f}_{ck}(\tau)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) d\tau \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \sin(2kx) \int_0^t (f_{sk}(\tau) - \bar{f}_{sk}(\tau)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) d\tau \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \sin(2kx) \int_0^t (f_{sk}(\tau) - \bar{f}_{sk}(\tau)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2(t-\tau)^\alpha) d\tau \end{aligned}$$

Applying Cauchy, Bessel inequality and taking maksimum of $u - \bar{u}$ lead to the following inequality for all $\alpha \in (0, 1]$

$$\|u - \bar{u}\| \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\varphi_0 - \bar{\varphi}_0\| + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \|\varphi_{ck} - \bar{\varphi}_{ck}\| + \|\varphi_{sk} - \bar{\varphi}_{sk}\| + M \|f - \bar{f}\|.$$

$$\|u - \bar{u}\| \leq \|\Phi - \bar{\Phi}\| + M \|f - \bar{f}\|,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi - \bar{\Phi}\| & = \frac{1}{2} \|\varphi_0 - \bar{\varphi}_0\| + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \|\varphi_{ck} - \bar{\varphi}_{ck}\| \\ & + \|\varphi_{sk} - \bar{\varphi}_{sk}\| \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $u \rightarrow \bar{u}$ as $\Phi \rightarrow \bar{\Phi}$, $f \rightarrow \bar{f}$.

Example:

$${}^C_0D_t^\alpha(u(x, t)) = u_{xx}(x, t) + f(x, t), x > 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1, t > 0,$$

$$u(0, t) = u(\pi, t),$$

$$u_x(0, t) = u_x(\pi, t),$$

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi(x) = 1 + \cos(2x),$$

where $f(x, t) = 2t(1 + \cos(2x)) + 4\cos(2x)$.
The pair of functions for $\alpha = 1$ is determined as

$$u(x, t) = (1 + \cos(2x))e^{t^2}$$

This problem can be solved by finite difference method.

5. Results and Discussion

In future studies, the suggested method will be utilized to construct the unknown function and solution for various fractional problems.

6. Conclusions

The existence, uniqueness and continuous dependence of data are achieved under certain regularity and consistency conditions. The obtained results are confirmed by an illustrative example.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

If the study does not require an Ethics Approval, the following declaration can be used:

“The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.”

Otherwise, please declare the board name granting ethics approval, approval date and approval number.

Conflict of Interest

All conflicts of interest should be declared. If there is not any conflict of interest, the content of this section can be arranged as follows.

“The authors declare that they have no known

competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.”

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